

Press release | May 2024

S3E hosts Start Open Day in iconic Lisbon theatre to unveil the selected deep tech projects from Southern Europe

The [Southern European Entrepreneurship Engine \(S3E\)](#) is hosting an Open Day on 18th June to introduce the 14 deep tech projects participating in the 2024 edition of S3E Start, the EU-funded programme of support for research teams and technology transfer officers in Southern Europe. The full event will be broadcasted live from the iconic Tivoli BBVA Theatre in Lisbon, Portugal.

After completing the 20-week programme of training and mentoring coordinated by [HiSeedTech](#), focused on building a lab-to-market business strategy for their science-based products, the pioneering research teams are now ready to introduce their deep tech solutions to the European innovation ecosystem.

During the celebration of the Start Open Day, a total of 14 teams — encompassing nearly 60 researchers from academic institutions in Spain, Portugal, Romania, Italy, Greece and Türkiye — will take centre stage at the Tivoli BBVA Theatre in Lisbon to showcase the groundbreaking solutions they've developed.

Explore all the projects that will be showcased at the open day on the [S3E website](#).

Tackling unmet or ill-met market needs, these solutions span across a wide spectrum of science fields, from agricultural sciences and engineering to life sciences. Additionally, the research teams will demonstrate how their solutions could positively impact social development and economic growth in Europe and beyond, directly addressing at least one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) set by the United Nations.

The S3E consortium kindly invites investors, business angels, and R&D organisations to join the live stream on Tuesday 18th June, at 14:30 Portuguese time (15:30 CEST), to meet the teams shaping the deep tech landscape in Southern Europe. Other researchers, accelerators, business support organisations and members of the general public are also welcome to attend online.

Attendees can check the full agenda and register [via this link](#).

About South European Entrepreneurship Engine:

[S3E](#) is an ambitious joint initiative funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe Programme. The consortium consists of 4 European partners from the research, innovation and acceleration ecosystem: [HiSeedTech](#) (Portugal), [Institute for Sustainable Development EPLO](#) (Greece), [International Development Ireland](#) (Ireland) and [AUSTRALO](#) (Spain). During the 30-month duration of the project, S3E aims to support 150+ deep tech ventures, including startups, SMEs, academic research teams and technology transfer offices based in Southern Europe.

Follow S3E on [X](#) and [LinkedIn](#) to stay up to date with the project's latest news, and subscribe to the [S3E newsletter](#) for upcoming opportunities for European startups to get involved.

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